

Flexible passive tag based on light energy harvesting for gas threshold determination in sealed environments

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Abstract

In this work we describe a passive screen printed flexible tag for gas monitoring that can be used in sealed environments. The developed measurement system is based on chemical sensors that are sensitive to gases concentration presenting optical response, luminescent or colourimetric. The measuring electronics consist of a LED for optical excitation of the sensing membrane and a high resolution digital colour detector for the reading of the optical signal. A microcontroller receives and processes the data enabling the detection threshold for the corresponding gas. The whole system is powered by two miniaturized solar cells that provide 4 V and up to 250 μ A each one. This system can run in sunlight or using a bright artificial light as the only energy source. The information of the inner environmental conditions regarding the gas concentration is transmitted to the user through a simple optical code using colour light-emitting diodes. These LEDs are activated to indicate whether the concentration of the monitored gas is within the expected limits, or not. Two prototypes based on this architecture and only changing the sensing module have been developed and applied for the determination of two common gases: oxygen and carbon dioxide. In the first case, a luminescent chemical sensor is used while in the second, the sensing membrane presents a colourimetric response. Both types of sensors can be used in this design. Resulting limits of detection are compatible with assessment of modified atmosphere packaging.

Keywords: Passive tag; Optical gas sensing; Colour detector; Light energy harvesting; Sealed environment sensing.

1. Introduction

Modification of the atmosphere composition in sealed environments is a common technique to improve the preservation of the contents. It is applied to prevent the inside from biological hazards, plagues, humidity, etc. In the food industry, modified atmosphere packaging (MAP) is traditionally used to preserve the freshness of fresh produce, meats and fish by controlling their biochemical metabolism [1, 2]. It is basically performed by injection of some gas or gas mixtures in the package with the objective of displacing or inhibiting others than can be detrimental to the content. Classical MAP technologies consist of nitrogen flushing, vacuum packaging and carbon dioxide injection [3, 4], and they have been used commercially for many years. Some recent MAP approaches make use of an inert gas (e.g. argon) flushing for fruits and vegetables [5], or carbon monoxide injection and high oxygen flushing for red meats [6].

Other sectors also draw upon atmosphere modification in enclosed environments with protection aims. For example, archaeological and art museums and private collections use storage in sealed chambers where the gas composition has been modified to avoid the deterioration of the items. The use of microclimate boxes with a modified gaseous content has become popular in the last decades. This interest arose from the need to reduce the deteriorating effects of oxygen [7]. The oxygen concentration in a microclimate box can be reduced to less than 0.05% as a method for the treatment of insect-infested museum objects. The Royal Mummy Collection at the Egyptian Museum is stored in sealed glass cases with an oxygen-reduced inert atmosphere of nitrogen at low relative humidity which suppresses both biological activity and oxidation in proteinaceous material [8]. In other cases, an atmosphere with high concentration of carbon dioxide about 60% is used to eliminate insect plagues in museums [9, 10].

In these modified and sealed atmospheres, it is of great importance to monitor the gas mixture composition, in order to maintain the gases proportion and detect small breaches or holes or its modification by bacterial activity. In some cases, this monitoring is accomplished by means of invasive methods such as the circulation of gas samples through pumps or needles to a gas analyzer and its later return to the sealed case [11, 12]. Nevertheless, this strategy is lately being replaced by non-invasive methods that maintain intact the sealing of the package or storage. This has the advantage that no package has to be sacrificed and therefore, it has an advantageous economic impact. These techniques are gaining great diffusion in the sector of intelligent or smart packaging of food and beverages. Intelligent packaging is an extension of the communication function of traditional packaging. It communicates information to the consumer based on its ability to sense, detect, or record external or internal changes in the product's environment. Examples include time-temperature indicators (TTI), gas leakage indicators, ripeness indicators, toxin indicators, biosensors, and radio frequency identification tags [13]. For the transmission to the user of the information regarding the atmosphere conditions inside the package, electronic circuitry is often included in the envelope [14, 15]. Radio frequency identification

(RFID) has been adopted as a major technology for the development of tags included or impressed on the packaging for the reading of the gas sensors and the transmission of the data to a remote RFID reader [16-18]. This technology presents the advantage of allowing the design of passive circuits that obtain the required power supply for the operation of the electronics from the near field generated by a remote RFID reader when it is approached to the tag [19, 20]. Therefore no battery is used in these tags, reducing the cost and extending its autonomy. Nevertheless, passive tags based on RFID require the inclusion of a large size antenna, usually screen-printed which limits the integration of the circuit. Moreover, the user needs an external RFID reader for its operation. In the last few years, these RFID passive tags have been combined with alternative sources of energy harvesting, specially solar energy, with the aim of maintaining the sensors working while there is no communication with an external RFID reader, or to increase the power supply for the whole system [21, 22]. Still, these designs are yet dependent on the presence of an external RFID reader and the integration of an antenna for wireless communication and energy harvesting.

In this work we describe a passive tag for gases determination based on optical chemical sensors that can be used in sealed environments. Unlike the mentioned designs based on RFID technology for data transmission and energy harvesting, the tag presented here is powered by means of two miniaturized solar cells. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first report of a passive tag for gas concentration measurement where the power supply relies only on light energy harvesting, and no other source of power supply such as batteries or near field energy harvesting is used, as it happens in the tags where RFID protocol is implemented. The results of the gas measurement are visually transmitted to the user through a simple colour code. This is done by means of colour light-emitting diodes (LEDs) that are activated to inform whether the monitored gas concentration is below or above a programmed limit. Therefore, this system acts as a threshold detector, which is enough for most of applications in the mentioned field.

The use of the proposed system can be extended for the determination of any gas if a corresponding chemical sensor with optical response, luminescent or colourimetric is included. In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed architecture, in this work two different tags based on this scheme and using both luminescent and colourimetric sensors have been developed for the monitoring of oxygen and carbon dioxide, two of the main gases employed in modified atmosphere techniques [23, 24].

2. Experimental

A. Reagents and materials

2-Hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC, average $M_v \sim 90,000$), meta-cresol purple sodium salt (MCP), glycerin, sodium bicarbonate, tetrahydrofuran (THF), platinum octaethylporphyrin (PtOEP), and polystyrene (PS, average MW 280 000; T_g , 100 °C; GPC grade) were all sourced from Sigma–Aldrich Química S.A. (Spain). As reflective layer white duct tape from 3M (Minnesota, USA) was used.

The tag is directly printed on 75 μm thick polyethylene naphthalate (PEN, Kaladex PEN Film, Dupont Teijin Films, Japan). This substrate was chosen because of its high optical transmission in the visible spectrum and good adherence. The screen-printing machine was a Serfix III (Seglevint S.L., Spain). The screen used to fabricate the single-layer pattern has a mesh density of 120 nylon threads per centimeter (T/cm). The conductive silver-based ink is CRSN 2442 (Sun Chemical Corporation, New Jersey, USA). After printing, the pattern was sintered at a constant temperature of 120°C for 5 min. To assemble the chips and external components to the substrate, a two-step process was carried out. First, the chips and silver pads were interconnected using the conductive resin H20E (Epoxy Technology, Inc., Massachusetts, USA). After this, the conductive resin was cured in an oven at 120 °C for 20 minutes.

B. Instruments and software

The electrical characterization of the system was carried out using the following laboratory instrumentation: a mixed signal oscilloscope (MSO4101, Tektronix, Oregon, USA), an 81/2-bit Digital Multimeter 3158A (Agilent Technologies, California, USA), a 15 MHz waveform generator 33120A (Agilent Technologies), a Precision Impedance Analyzer 4294A and an impedance probe kit (4294A1) (Agilent Technologies), a DC power supply E3630A (Agilent Technologies) and a balance DV215CD (Ohaus Co., New Jersey, USA). A user interface made in Visual Basic was used in a computer for calibration purposes. The standard mixtures for instrument calibration and characterization were prepared using N₂ as the inert gas by controlling the flow rates of the different high purity gases O₂, CO₂ and N₂, entering a mixing chamber using a computer-controlled mass flow controller (Air Liquid España S.A., Spain) operating at a total pressure of 760 Torr and a flow rate of 500 cm³ min⁻¹.

C. System description

1) Membranes preparation

Sensing membranes containing luminophore for O₂ were prepared from a cocktail that contains 100 mg of PS dissolved in 1 mL of freshly distilled THF, using an ultrasonic bath, and 0.5 mg PtOEP. The sensor preparation consists of the casting on one side of the support with 20 μL of cocktail A. After that, the support was left to dry in darkness in a desiccator that had a saturated THF atmosphere for 1 hour at room temperature [25].

Sensing membranes for CO₂ were prepared from a cocktail containing 12.5 mg of HEC, 1.4 mg MCP, 2.25 mg NaHCO₃ and 37.5 mg glycerin all dissolved in 1 mL of water, using an ultrasonic bath. The sensor preparation consists of the casting on one side of the Mylar support with 20 μL of cocktail B. After that, the support was left to dry in darkness in a desiccator for 6 h at room temperature.

2) *Description of the instrument*

The novel architecture consists of a small electronic tag screen printed on a flexible substrate of dimensions $38 \times 19 \text{ mm}^2$. This tag is intended to be attached on the external surface of the sealed case that contains the modified atmosphere to be monitored, or it can even be directly printed on the envelope of the package. The optical gas sensor is printed or deposited on the inner surface of the cage or container, aligned with the sensing electronics. This measurement technique has been previously described by the authors [19].

As explained above in the Introduction section, the objective of this work is to develop a flexible screen printed passive tag that does not require the use of RFID technology for the communication with the user. The benefits of this approach are the elimination of the large-size antenna needed in this protocol and an easier interaction with the user because it does not require an external RFID reader to power the tag and obtain the data. This implies that any non-expert user can read the information provided by the tag. The approach followed in this work for generating the power supply of the prototype is based on light energy harvesting. The whole design is based on the specification that the system is powered through two mini solar cells model CPC1824 (IXYS Integrated Circuits Division, California, USA). Each cell provides an output of 4 V and a current up to 100 μA at direct sunlight (6000 lux), according to the manufacturer specifications. Nevertheless, it has been proved that a bright light with intensity higher than 6000 lux produces an output current up to 250 μA , value that depends on the intensity of the incident light and the load applied to the cells. Figure 1 shows the electrical characterization of a single solar cell in terms of output current I and power P versus output voltage V when it is illuminated by the light source used in this study. The light source is a 5 watt compact LED hand torch that contains a white LED model CREE XPG R5 (Cree, Inc. North Carolina, USA). This device generates a white light with an intensity of 400 lumen. The maximum available output power under these conditions is achieved at the Maximum Power Point (MPP), which in this case is 0.8 mW at 3.7 V. Due to the selection of components of ultra low power consumption the maximum power required for our tag is around 1.5 mW. Therefore, at least two solar cells must be included in the design to generate a maximum power of 1.6 mW. When these two cells are arranged in parallel configuration, the output voltage of the structure is 4V, and the supplied current is 190 μA , which is very close to the MPP, as it can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Electrical characterization of a single solar cell illuminated in the tests conditions.

The sensing module of the system is composed of an excitation LED and a high resolution digital colour detector. The LED must be selected according to the application of the system, i.e., the chemical sensor used to measure a given gas. If the sensor presents luminescent response, that is, it emits a luminescence when it is excited at a given wavelength, the LED is chosen to excite at this particular excitation wavelength. If the sensor used is a colourimetric one, i.e. it shows colour variation with the concentration of the gas, the LED selected is white. A digital colour detector is used to register the optical response of the chemical sensor. The model used in this design is the S11059-02DT (Hamamatsu Photonics, Japan), which is an I²C interface-compatible colour detector sensitive to red ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=615$ nm), green ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=530$ nm), blue ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=460$ nm), and infrared ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=855$ nm) radiation. It outputs detected results as 16-bit digital data for each colour. Besides its high resolution and compatibility, it has been selected over other detectors used in previous works [19, 26] due to its very low power consumption (250 μ W in operation mode), which makes this device optimal for passive designs. The output of the colour detector is serially sent as digital words to the microcontroller model PIC16LF1703 (Microchip Technology Inc., Arizona, USA). This device is selected because of its extreme low-power features such as an operating current in the range of microamperes. A temperature sensor model MCP9700A (Microchip Technology Inc.) is included in the design. This sensor presents an accuracy of $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a very low current consumption of 6 μ A. A temperature sensor is necessary when the chemical sensor used in a given application presents temperature drifts that have to be corrected by the microcontroller [27].

Both the colour detector and the microcontroller are digital components, so they are not affected by variations in the power supply provided by the solar cells that can arise from

changes in the intensity or angle of the incident light, as long as the voltage and current are enough to allow their operation. The temperature sensor is an analog device, but it shows a stable output that is not affected by variations in the power supply, as long as it remains above 2.3 V to keep the sensor activated. The only device that could produce a misreading of the gas concentration if variations in the output voltage and current of the solar cells are produced is the excitation LED. The intensity of the light emitted by this LED affects the response of the optical chemical sensor when it is luminescent type, or directly the measurement of the colour detector when the sensor presents a colourimetric response. The emission of the excitation LED must be stable, but it depends on its polarization current and voltage. Therefore, a voltage reference consisting of a Zener diode is included in the design, configured in parallel to the excitation LED, as it is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Polarization of the excitation LED

The Zener diode is reverse polarized, establishing a voltage drop of V_z from anode to cathode of the excitation LED. This voltage drop must match the required polarization voltage for the excitation LED, so both Zener and LED diodes must be designed to be complementary. With the structure depicted in Figure 2, variations in the output voltage caused by the solar cells are absorbed by the serial resistance, while variations in the output current are absorbed by the Zener diode. In that way, the polarization of the excitation LED remains fully stable.

Figure 3 presents a photography of a generic developed tag based on the described scheme. As it has been explained above, the selection of the excitation LED and the associate Zener diode depends on the specific application of the tag, and more particularly, on the optical gas sensor included in the system. The rest of the components are common to any tag developed following the presented architecture.

Figure 3. Photography showing the different smart tag components. The white circle indicates the region where the sensing membrane is placed.

When the sensing module performs a measurement, the data regarding the colour detection and temperature are received by the microcontroller, where the calibration curves are previously stored. The microcontroller generates an estimation of the gas concentration based on these data and the result is compared to a pre-established threshold that determines whether the concentration is correct inside the sealed environment or not. The microcontroller activates the green or red LED to inform the user about the result of this measurement, therefore making unnecessary the presence of a wireless data transmission protocol such as RFID.

3. Results and Discussion

The measurement platform described in the previous section has been applied to the determination of two common gases in modified atmospheres, namely oxygen and carbon dioxide. The system is able to monitor only one gas, hence two different tags have been developed in order to measure O_2 and CO_2 . The gas sensors employed present different optical responses; therefore the configuration of the tags must be distinct, as it is explained below.

In the case of O_2 , a chemical sensor based on luminescence quenching of the complex PtOEP is used. This sensor has a long lifetime, the long term stability of luminophore membranes shows a phosphorescence decreases by some 20% after 210 days [27] and a low price of $3.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ € per sensing membrane.

This luminophore produces an emission at the wavelength of 645 nm corresponding to red region of the visible spectrum when it is optically excited at 537 nm, which corresponds to green light [28]. An excitation LED model SMP2-UPGC (Bivar Inc., California, USA.) with peak emission at 536 nm is used due to its low power

consumption. For a direct polarization voltage of 2.5 V, this LED requires a low current of only 40 μA . The corresponding Zener diode used to fix the polarization of the excitation LED to 2.5 V according to Figure 2 is the model LM285-2.5-N (Texas Instruments, Texas, USA) which is reverse polarized with a small current of 20 μA .

Figure 4. Sensing set-ups showing the excitation and reading devices of the O_2 sensor (A) and CO_2 sensor (B)

The emitted luminescence of the oxygen sensitive luminophore in response to the optical excitation is captured with the colour detector as it is schematized in the Figure 4A. The output digital word corresponding to the red component of the colour detector is a direct measurement of the intensity [26] when the system is optically isolated. The internal filters of the colour detector avoid the influence of the excitation green light on the measurement of the luminescence emitted by the oxygen sensor, since the output of this device corresponding to the incident red light is only affected by this luminescence. The intensity of this luminescence under stable optical excitation is attenuated when the concentration of the surrounding oxygen increases, as it is shown in the Figure 5A.

Figure 5. Optical response of the O_2 (A) and CO_2 (B) sensors.

This system has been calibrated in the full range 0–100%, with 6 replicas at room temperature (21°C) for each concentration. For data acquisition, the microcontroller programmer model Pickit 3 (Microchip Technology Inc.) is configured in debugger mode and used to obtain the colour measurements. The results are shown in Figure 6, where logarithmic scale in the vertical axis is used for a better visualization of the data. Error bars are included in the graphic but they are too small to be appreciated. The intensity is directly taken as the red coordinate reading from the colour detector when a stable optical excitation is applied.

Figure 6. Calibration curve of the system with the O₂ sensor.

As it was expected, the measured data can be fitted to a potential curve in the form [24, 26] $I = \alpha \cdot [O_2]^\beta$, with $\alpha = 16136.42$ and $\beta = -0.5894$, being the coefficient of correlation, $R^2 = 0.9958$.

The CO₂ sensor is based on the acidity of this molecule [29]. The sensor contains an acid-base indicator (MCP) showing an optical response in the form of colour variations when the concentration of the surrounding CO₂ changes. The colour of this sensor varies from dark blue to yellow when the concentration of carbon dioxide raises from 0 to 100% as it is shown in Figure 5B. This sensor has been proved to be stable for 9 months [30]. It also has a very low cost of $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ € per sensing membrane.

The advantages of using of water-based sensors instead of the widely used organic-based sensors for CO₂ are their less toxicity and higher stability since quaternary ammonium salts are not used [25]. These characteristics gain great importance especially for food industry applications. The drawback of CO₂ water-based sensors compared to organic-based sensors is the higher response times [30].

Since the response of this sensor is colourimetric, the measurement protocol is slightly different than the previous case. Figure 4B presents the arrangement of the sensing module in the case of colourimetric sensors. Here the excitation LED used is white, considering that the parameter to be determined now is the colour of the membrane. The model of the LED used is LW-QH8G (OSRAM Licht AG, Germany), which can be polarized at 2.5 V with a low current of 30 μ A. Being the polarization voltage the same as the one in the configuration for the oxygen sensor, the same Zener diode is used. Since the excitation and detection devices are placed on the same side of the tag, the colour measurement is carried out by reflection of the emitted white light. As it is depicted in the Figure 4B, a reflective layer is attached to the gas sensitive membrane. This layer consists simply of a white porous adhesive paper that allows the flux of gas through it.

Using this configuration of the tag, the CO₂ sensor has been calibrated in the full range 0 to 100%. To quantify the colour variation of the membrane, an intensity parameter has been defined from the values of the R, G and B coordinates given by the colour detector [31]:

$$I = \sqrt{R^2 + G^2 + B^2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 7 presents the data obtained in the calibration process.

Figure 7. Calibration of the system with the CO₂ sensor.

In this case, the measured data can be again fitted to a potential curve in the form $I = \alpha \cdot [\text{CO}_2]^\beta$, being now $\alpha = 1506.12$ and $\beta = 0.0828$, and $R^2 = 0.9955$.

The resolution of this system can be obtained from the potential curves found in the fitting of the experimental data, taking derivatives in both sides of the equation and

approximating these derivatives to increments [28]. By doing so, the obtained expression for the resolution is:

$$\Delta X = \frac{\left(\frac{I}{\alpha}\right)^{1/\beta}}{\beta I} \Delta I \quad (2)$$

where X is the concentration of O_2 or CO_2 and ΔI is the error or uncertainty in the determination of the intensity I . This intensity is defined as the value of the red component of the detected light in the case of the oxygen sensor. Therefore, for this case, $\Delta I = \Delta R$ is the resolution in the quantification of the R coordinate. In the case of the carbon dioxide sensor, the intensity is defined as expressed in Equation 1. The uncertainty in the determination of this intensity is calculated by taking derivatives again:

$$\Delta I = \frac{R}{I} \Delta R + \frac{G}{I} \Delta G + \frac{B}{I} \Delta B \quad (3)$$

In the ideal case where no external source of error in the measurement of the gas affects the response of the system, the errors ΔR , ΔG and ΔB are given by the resolution of the colour detector, that is, $1/2^{16}$ which means an error of $2.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$ % of full scale since this device codifies the measured light in 16-bits words. In practice, the response of the system is affected by small instabilities of the concentration in the gases mixture surrounding the gas sensor, temperature drifts, etc. The experimental resolution in this study is calculated by taking the errors ΔR , ΔG and ΔB as the standard deviation of the measurements for six replicas, which take values in the range $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ % to $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ % of full scale. These uncertainties are much higher than the used in the theoretical study; therefore significative differences in the theoretical and experimental resolutions are expected.

The limit of detection (LOD) was obtained using the standard criteria: $LOD = y_b + 3s_b$, where y_b is the average blank signal and s_b is the standard deviation of the blank, which is determined using at least 10 replicas.

Table 1 presents the obtained values of resolution and LOD for both study cases.

Gas	Theoretical resolution (ppm)	Experimental resolution (ppm)	LOD (ppm)
O_2	1.3×10^{-5} (at 1%)	6.4 (at 1%)	170
	1.6×10^{-3} (at 21%)	100 (at 21%)	
	3.4×10^{-2} (at 100%)	2057 (at 100%)	
CO_2	1.4×10^{-3} (at 0.5%)	93 (at 0.5%)	720
	2.2×10^{-2} (at 15%)	1416 (at 15%)	
	1.5×10^{-1} (at 100%)	9594 (at 100%)	

Table 1. Resolution and LOD of the two tags.

As it can be seen, very good specifications are achieved with the presented system. In particular, the low values of the LOD in oxygen and carbon dioxide, 170 ppm (0.017%) and 720 ppm (0.072%) respectively, make the developed tag optimal for its use in the determination of the concentration of these gases in sealed environments such as microclimate boxes or MAPs. In these cases, the O₂ concentration can be reduced up to a 0.05%, and the CO₂ is usually maintained above 2%. The limits achieved with the presented system cover these values more than enough, so a high resolution threshold detector can be implemented with the proposed tag for any application in modified atmospheres controlling.

4. Conclusions

In this work the architecture of a full passive tag for the detection of gas threshold concentration in sealed environments is presented. The power supply is provided by means of two mini solar cells that are able to harvest light energy from solar radiation or from a bright artificial light source such as a hand torch. The selection of very low consumption components for the measurement electronics allow the use of this power source, with a total power consumption below 1.6 mW. The determination of the gas concentration is based on chemical sensors with optical response that is registered through a high resolution digital colour detector. This system has been evaluated for the measurement of two gases O₂ and CO₂, by means of two different developed tags, although any gas sensor showing optical response can be used. Results show that a high experimental resolution of 6.4 and 93 ppm in the best case, and a low limit of detection of 170 and 720 ppm for oxygen and carbon dioxide respectively, are achieved using both luminescent and colourimetric sensors. A threshold of gas concentration can be programmed in the microcontroller, and the system generates an optical output through green and red LEDs to inform the user if the monitored gas inside the package or cage is below of above this limit.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on an electronic system with these characteristics which does not require the use of a RFID protocol for data transmission and energy harvesting, relying the power supply only on light energy harvesting. The use of this tag covers a wide range of applications in different areas where the monitoring of gases composition in modified atmospheres is required.

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